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**MAKING SENSE OF CONSTELLATIONS OF OBJECTS
A CASE STUDY OF COMPUTER-AIDED WRITING PRACTICES IN THEATRICAL
STAGING**

Annie Gentes, Professor
Co-Design Lab & Media Studies, Telecom ParisTech
annie.gentes@telecom-paristech.fr

Mathias Béjean, PhD, Research fellow
Centre de Gestion Scientifique, Mines ParisTech
Mines ParisTech Chair for "Theories and Methods for innovative design"

ABSTRACT

This paper aims to understand how various media are needed to anticipate a future object and how the design process therefore relies on making sense of a constellation of objects. To do so, we explore the case of a show created in 2002 by French artist Michel Jaffrennou. Based on a longitudinal study, we analyse how various writing tools shape documents in specific ways. Revealing that each document contributes to unveil certain aspects of the object-to-be, our study also uses a semiotic analysis to analyze how each document imposes a "definition" of what a show "is", which could prove insufficient to the practice of staging. By suggesting how a "constellation of objects" may avoid this pitfall, for it builds a heterogeneous point of view that conveys the richness of the expected show, our study contributes to a wider discussion on the links between objects and anticipation in projects of design.

Keywords: heterogeneity - objects - semiotics - project of design

INTRODUCTION

One way to tackle the issue of "diversity and unity" in design processes is to consider the concept of "heterogeneity." In social sciences, this concept has recently received a renewed interest in so far as developed societies gather ever more heterogeneous actors and objects within the same "places", be it on a real or virtual basis. In this paper, we would like to

contribute to this discussion by developing a comprehensive understanding of how designers can make sense of heterogeneous objects in their design work.

Recent research in both organization and design studies has already contributed to deepening our understanding of heterogeneity at work. Influenced by Star's and Griesemer's (1989) seminal article on scientific work, many organization scientists have explored how heterogeneous actors may use "boundary objects" to collaborate with each other at work (e.g. Carlile, 2002). Boundary objects are those mediating objects that are sufficiently consistent to carry specific knowledge, but, at the same time, sufficiently generic to cross boundaries between different and intersecting social worlds. Approaches inspired by this framing thus consider the concept of heterogeneity in terms of "actors" who have different interests, knowledge or practices, but who can nonetheless cooperate at work, especially by resorting to boundary objects.

However, while pointing to the role of objects, medias and artefacts in collaborative processes, sociological research works tend to overlook the variety of such objects that is often required at work, especially in the context of design projects (Ewenstein & Whyte, 2009). In line with other design studies we would like to draw attention to the rich constellation of objects that is often needed to make sense of design work (Béjean, 2008; Gentès, 2008).

Following Bucciarelli (Bucciarelli, 2002) on object and language worlds, we believe that each media, whether a sketch, a prototype, a bit of code, brings its own model of what the design project is. In other words, each media presents a certain way of anticipating how the design project is going to be materialized. Hence the objective of this paper is not to study how one object or artefact may sustain one specific class of organizational or cognitive processes. The objective of this paper is rather to understand how the very diversity of media is needed in this process of anticipation because each media shapes the way we understand the object-to-be in a specific way. More specifically, we want to understand: (i) how each media contributes to unveil certain aspects of the object-to-be through a semiotic analysis and (ii) how one media is used to counterbalance the limitations of another.

We explore these issues by considering the case of computer-aided practices in theatrical staging. In particular we conducted an ethnographic study on the process of creation of a show created by French artist Michel Jaffrennou. Focusing on the symbolic registers (Peirce, 1978) mobilized by the different writing tools that were used by the artist to achieve the staging of the show, our case study provides an empirically based account on how designers can make sense of heterogeneous objects to accomplish their design work.

This paper is set out as follows: in a first section we explain the theoretical background to this study. Then, in a second section we describe our research methods and approach to the selected case. In a third section, we provide our empirical findings and suggest an interpretation that is finally discussed in the fourth and concluding section.

THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

In this section, we clarify the theoretical foundation to this study. After delineating our understanding of processes of signification, we explain our approach to the symbolic functioning of "objects" in computer-aided writing processes.

A PEIRCIAN UNDERSTANDING OF PROCESSES OF SIGNIFICATION

Our analysis of processes of signification is based on Peirce's semiotics (Peirce, 1978) that identifies three registers of significance. First, Peirce defines the register of "firstness" as the individual relation to a phenomenon. This is the abstract quality of any perception or memorization: it is a vague and unanalyzed impression of something possible out of its realization. The category of quality is focused on individuals (not communities). Second, Peirce names "secondness" a register of significance that corresponds to facts, existing, updated phenomena, events, spatio-temporally determined and initiating a relationship. As pointed out by Babou and Le Marec (Le Marec & Babou, 2003), "expressed in sociological or anthropological terms, the "secondness", the register of facts or relationships, can be interpreted as the category that depicts the dynamics of change: it is the balance of relations between actors in a system that shapes the device that they drive, the evolution of its signifying forms" (242-243). Finally, "thirdness" is about structure and institutions that stabilize meaning and understanding. It is about social conventions and the way texts shape our representations.

OBJECTS IN COMPUTER-AIDED WRITING PROCESSES: THE CONCEPT OF "ARCHITEXT"

In this paper, we consider "objects" not only in terms of their symbolic content or potential materiality, but also in terms of symbolic functioning. We are thus interested by the way objects function as "actants" that influence the way we anticipate a project, experience aesthetically the project (Latour, 1999) in a wider symbolic system. Following Jeanneret (2008), we here suggest to name this kind of symbolic systems a "constellation of objects", be it a set of virtual representations or physical artefacts.

Furthermore, past research on computer-aided writing processes, has shown that software function as "architext" that organize the writing process. The word was first used by Genette (1979, p. 12-13) to describe rhetorical patterns that underlie a group of texts. In design studies, it has then been developed

by Jeanneret and Souchier (2003) as the tangible and visual pre-organization of a text as it appears in the window of laptops, with signs, tabs, rulings, and a model of text (typically professional and not a rough copy). The etymology of the word *architext* points to the idea of a beginning (the writer is not confronted to a white page) and of management (the process is spatially and temporally planned).

As the *architext* organizes the physical practice of writing, the question emphasized by a number of artists (for instance those who participated in the CODEeDOC exhibition in 2002), designers (John Maeda) and information scientists is whether this set-up of documents and this command of writing does standardize expression or does not (Jeanneret, 2008). The debate is positioned between proponents of designing one's own tools (as was John Maeda's position) and advocates of using these *architexts* with a certain critical distance (Gentès & Braun, 2005).

Regarding our study, what is clear is that an *architext* is not a neutral tool. It incorporates relations and opposition: neat document opposed to rough sketch (secondness), and institutions: professional dactilography and publishing industry versus private writing space (thirdness). For example, Tufte (2003) or Laufer (1993) demonstrated that such writing software as *Powerpoint* incorporates professional practices and legitimizes certain types of writing within institutions.

RESEARCH METHODS

As we wanted to explore heterogeneity at work, we opted for a longitudinal, ethnographic approach. The field was delimited by the artist, the producer and the professors who organized the workshop. The workshop lasted three months and mainly consisted of three weekly meetings of three hours between the stage director, twelve engineering students, two professors of computer sciences with experience in new media art, a professor of humanities (trained in literature, art and social sciences). The meetings could also include the producer, specialized in multimedia shows, and one assistant of production.

The first sessions were organized as brainstorming sessions that issued a first text (word document) that was the starting point for the process of reformulation. Then, between each session, students had to prepare a draft in a new format that was discussed, amended or rewritten during the session. The students chose this particular workshop out of an interest for creative and artistic activities. A survey of their background and interests showed that in addition to their scientific training they practiced either photography, music, or the theater. Plus, they benefited from the classical training in humanities that the French system of education imposes. In other words, they all had a more or less developed culture in French classical theater from Corneille, Racine, Molière, up to Anouilh or Sartre. They had heard about the rules of classical theater: unity of action, time and place. They all had a traditional understanding of the theater as a written text that can be read as a series of dialogues and that is eventually staged with a certain leeway as for the props, costumes, etc. (elements that appear secondary to the text). Finally, they read Goethe's *Faust* that was to be the inspiration for the show. Coming from a contemporary branch of theater that combines different traditions (in particular, Antonin Artaud *le Théâtre et son double*) Jaffrenou offered a quite different viewpoint on the theater. In particular, very much influenced by the circus tradition, he emphasized the physical impact of theater and its magical inspiration. The workshop was therefore both and at the same time a creative and learning process for the group that had to come up with a truly artistic proposal with interesting technical features.

DATA COLLECTION

Data collection consisted in two main phases. The first one was dedicated to the characterization of what is a "staging process." In addition to general documentation in stage management, we conducted several interviews with the artist to produce a comprehensive understanding of his staging practice. The second phase of data collection was then dedicated to participative observation during the staging process. The first author was deeply involved in this longitudinal study. She collected "composites" (Le Marec et al., 2003), that is to say

data that gathered discursive and material artifacts. These data were then examined with the collaboration of the second author. Both authors participated in the data analysis process.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis consisted in three interrelated phases. First, we used the first data collection to produce a simplified model of a "staging process." This led us to identify the basic elements of such processes, including all visual aspects (structure of the stage, scenic background, light and sound effects, costumes,...) but also symbolic and performing aspects (actors' positions, gestures on stage, potential interactions with the audience,...).

Second, we characterized the data coming from the participative observation by using Peirce's analytical framework on the registers of significance (i.e. firstness, secondness, thirdness). This allowed us to analyze the different documents under study (Word texts, Excel tables, Html pages, Flowcharts, Director models) not only in terms of technical aspects, but also in terms of their symbolic functioning, i.e. as "architexts." This helped us to characterize their properties for each different semiotic registers that they were mobilizing (Babou, 2008). For example, we detailed properties of firstness, secondness and thirdness for each architext.

Third, we analyzed the contribution to the writing process of each architexts by using our simplified model of the staging process. For example, we tried to understand how one architext may influence one or several visual or performing aspects of the staging-to-be. It should be noted that while being sequential to some extent, our case study was also iterative, which often induced us to test and revise our assumptions and findings all along the process of investigation.

CASE SELECTION

The case was selected for three main reasons. First, the observation could take place at the very beginning of the project, which seems a condition for the success of our longitudinal approach. Second, the group that participated to the project under study accepted that the first author could carry out

an in-depth empirical study, which was another necessary condition to sustain our comprehensive approach to design practices at work. Third, the artist was already engaged in a reflection on the use of different objects in his staging practices. We thus had the opportunity to observe a very pioneering and insightful case on how computer-aided writing practices may make use of constellations of objects.

RESEARCH BACKGROUND

In 2002, two researchers from the Department of Computer science of French Engineering School, Telecom ParisTech invited their students to participate in the early design phases of a live, interactive performance, "Mephisto Circus", to be held simultaneously on three separate locations connected with a (VTHD) broadband network. They worked with the French filmmaker and multimedia artist Michel Jaffrennou and with the company Gaia and its director Guilhem Pratz.

Michel Jaffrennou is a video and a multimedia artist (Méredieu, 2003) who has worked on the mix between real and virtual on stages in particular for such shows as "Le Petit Théâtre de Diguiden" (Diguiden's Small Theater). It should be noted that Michael Jaffrennou worked with renowned sociologist Bruno Latour. They share an interest in the format of the "grid" that Latour studied in his book on scientific methods (Latour, 1999) and that Jaffrennou used so as to try different combinations of items. In particular Jaffrennou used Latour's concept of pedocomparator defined as follows : "*in the regularity of its cube, their disposition in columns and rows, their discrete character, and the possibility of freely substituting one column for another, the pedocomparator belongs to sign. Or rather, it is through the cunning invention of this hybrid that the world of things may become a sign*" (Latour, 1999, p.48).

The school wanted to test its broadband network but also wanted to explore the aesthetic and social potential of connecting three spaces that were both virtual and real. Apart from the technical specifications related to the implementation of a broadband network, the group was free to imagine the scenario that was finally based on Goethe's play

“Faust” (1829-1832), hence the name of the show: “Mephisto Circus” .

Michel Jaffrennou consequently organized a creative writing workshop that addressed not only the difficulty of anticipating a complex multimedia show but also questioned the relevance of computer softwares to design such a performance. It should be noted that “Mephisto Circus” was eventually not produced for a number of reasons, including the cost of such an operation and the difficulty of adapting the available places (conference rooms or class rooms of the connected institutions in Sophia-Antipolis - close to Nice, Paris, and Brest) to the needs of the theater (backstage, complete darkness, etc.). Nevertheless, the artist incorporated some of these ideas for example in *The Phantom Public*, 2005, a work by Michel Jaffrennou and Thierry Coduys whereby the public could vary the lighting and sound of the exhibition at whim (Art Forum, December 2005).

CASE STUDY

CASE EVIDENCE

To create the show, Jaffrennou and Pratz resorted to their methodology of creation. They did not use one particular architext but a diversity of writing softwares or media that produced different presentations, anticipations, and perspectives of the show-to-be. Each document was subsequently discussed by the group with the artists to evaluate the benefit of the results. The group wrote several scenarios not primarily to decide of the final form of “Mephisto Circus” but rather to explore and to bring out the show in different forms.

First, the group used the word processor “Word” as the more “natural” tool to tell a story. It allowed the group to describe the characters as well as create the dialogues. This use comforted the assumption that a show is a sequence of actions, as it is mostly taught in French education. This document also reassured the engineering researchers who are used to writing scenario of uses that describe a sequence of events. This assumption would be questioned and even rejected in the course of the project. In

particular, this form of writing cannot easily insert public participation.

To take into consideration and to materialize the interactive dimension of the show, the group wrote the show with a flow chart (see figure 1) which enhanced the temporal structure of the show and its optional features. Each contribution of the public appeared as a branching in the narration of the show. For instance, if the audience lighted the stage, then Mephisto disappeared. If the audience left the semidarkness, Mephisto continued to play.

Figure 1 - Flowchart

But this representation could not describe the public as actors, in particular what motivated their participation, or what were the tools of their intervention. It also could not illustrate how the show worked as a magic theater with virtual and real objects appearing and disappearing in between the three local stages. Writing a webpage for each stage of the show appeared to solve this problem, while

keeping some of the dynamics of the flow chart (see figure 2).

Figure 2 - Webpage

HARMONIE

Description brève de la fiche

[Paris](#) [Brest](#) [Nice](#)

Totems	?		
Ecrans	Actifs.		
Acteur	Absent.		
Lumières	ambiance lumineuse		
Son	ambiance sonore		
Éléments utilisés	liste des éléments déjà utilisés		
Action	Les spectateurs utilisent les technologies de manière harmonieuse. Les différentes salles ont choisi de collaborer pour que le spectacle reste vivable. <u>Mephisto est vaincu, l'élaboration d'un document collectif entre les salles vient sceller cette union qui permet de rejeter Mephisto.</u>		
<i>Description de la suite 1</i>	<i>Description de la suite 2</i>	<i>Description de la suite 3</i>	
Suite 1	Suite 2	Suite 3	

The use of "Excel" (see figure 3) took the group beyond the notion of the stage as a symbolic environment, to focus on the place as a constellation of technical equipment and people. Jaffrennou indeed developed his own creative tool based on a spreadsheet with columns organized by elements (lists of possible landscapes, characters, objects, etc.). He used this method to create ideas of scenarios by associations. The show was written again with the spreadsheet, taking into consideration all the "objects" and places as "actants" (Latour, 1999) of the show. However, with this architext it was impossible to put the various protagonists on stage.

Figure 3 - Excel

	A	C	D	E	F	G
	EXPOLOGIE	SCENARIO	EVALUATION	TRAITEMENT ONI	QUI/QUOI ?	minutes OO1
3	HORMAIN/ACTEUR	scenar/acteur-1		ordres.ecrits	acteur1	premiateur1
4	HORMAIN/ACTEUR	scenar/acteur-2		ordres.ecrits	acteur2	premiateur2
5	HORMAIN/ACTEUR	scenar/acteur-3		ordres.ecrits	acteur3	premiateur3
6						
7	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-1			filapghon	
8	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-2			filapghon	
9	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-3			filapghon	
10	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-4			filapghon	
11	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-5			filapghon	
12	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-6			filapghon	
13	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-7			filapghon	
14	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-8			filapghon	
15	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FI/ONE	scenar/te/spect-9			filapghon	
16						
17	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-1			objjet1	
18	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-2			objjet1	
19	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-3			objjet1	
20	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-4			objjet1	
21	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-5			objjet1	
22	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-6			objjet2	
23	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-7			objjet2	
24	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-8			objjet2	
25	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-9			objjet3	
26	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-10		Range/Actessa 1	objjet3	
27	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-11		Range/Actessa 2	objjet3	
28	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-12		Range/Actessa 3	objjet3	
29	HORMAIN/TECH/SPECT/FO/LE/T	scenar/fo/obj-13			objjet3	
30						

To consider the spatial dimension of the show itself, Jaffrennou finally used "Director" (see figure 4) that allowed him to put the different tangible artifacts into perspective. Eventually, the group realized that they were limited by the sheer size of the printing paper. The size of the sheet or paper - even A3 - proved woefully inadequate for an overview of the project.

Figure 4 - Director

CASE INTERPRETATION

In our view, this case well illustrates how architexts impose a certain form of writing that conceals or displays aspects of the project of design (here, the show) as well as create expectations about its nature. Each architext proposed a relation to stage, actors, spectators, and made sense in this particular instance. The writing process was precisely based on the tension between different representations of the show. In our case, each architext was successively used so as to uncover new dimensions of the show or to reformulate the same elements therefore giving them a new significance. The different writing tools and associated documents: word processing, spreadsheet, graphics animation (Director), web pages, exposed the show in their own specific way that seemed quite satisfactory each time but which proved to be partial and did not allow to fully apprehend the expected result.

Each tool produced different results that not only built the show differently but also questioned the

presuppositions of what "is" a show. We could finally mention all elements of our show in each document but the different visualizations helped to anticipate and emphasize aspects of the show differently. First, using different tools showed the limitation of each one in particular to anticipate what a show could be. Then each tool reinforced a certain vision of what a show is. Obviously, the theater was not only a text that is read then staged as if one switched from 2D to 3D. Finally, each writing of the show produced changes on several levels: the story, stage management, use of the technology and artifacts, audience's modalities of intervention. Each state of "stability" acquired through one tool was therefore challenged by a new period of writing with a different tool not only because it added new elements but also because it changed the viewpoint on these elements. In addition, the writing process also organized the collaboration within the group. While participants had no constraint on the scenario, the use of a common tool forced them to adjust to each other.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In the design process, the first stage was therefore not to produce a unified vision of the object to be but make sure that no features are ignored or omitted because writing tools offer a biased and limited view of the object-to-be. Architexts not only shape the object in a certain way, they are based on models of activity that can be inadequate for the object-to-be. They are symbolic frames that supports forms of legitimacy but also promote views of what is the relation between text and the final object. Bucciarelli (2002) points to the notion of languages that emphasizes the idea that cultures shape the way we look at things and produce them. But the notion of media and architext insists on the forms and political agenda that are always present in these writing apparatus.

The notion of "project" therefore must be questioned in the light of these practices. The show could not be defined in advance as if the actual staging would be the mere projection of the programmatic documents.

More generally, design as the process that deploys the potential of structures, organizations, media, as defined by Moholy Nagy (*Vision in Motion*, 1947) shows here a new "relevance". In Moholy Nagy's vision, the design process is about exploring how different structures produce different versions of objects even if the final objects share the same functions.

As pointed out by the philosopher of design, Pierre-Damien Huyghe (2006), design is within the industry, the activity that explores and deploys the diversity of means of conception and production. In the case of the anticipation of an object, the exploration of writing tools and the use of their various productions is therefore more than an economic question. Within the writing process, the artist and the producer actually shaped the show and not only programmed it. Each document is a facet of the show: they contribute to a cubist view of the show that gradually shapes it. Each document feeds the other in an iterative movement. As a result, while carrying the traditional limitations of any single case study, our study provides new insights on the links between heterogeneity, objects and anticipation in "projects of design" (Findeli, 1995).

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